

DOI: 10.15276/ETR.02.2021.3
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5115796
UDC: 315: [314.15:343.6]
JEL: F22, O15

ANALYSIS OF ILLEGAL MIGRATION AND GOVERNMENT POLICY TO ELIMINATE IT

АНАЛІЗ НЕЛЕГАЛЬНОЇ МІГРАЦІЇ ТА ДЕРЖАВНА ПОЛІТИКА ЩОДО ЇЇ УСУНЕННЯ

Natalia A. Dobrianska, DEcon, Professor
Odessa National Polytechnic University, Odessa, Ukraine
ORCID: 0000-0002-0826-8840
Email: semen-198@te.net.ua

Alina A. Demyanyuk
Odessa National Polytechnic University, Odessa, Ukraine
ORCID: 0000-0001-5509-1403
Email: demanukalina@gmail.com

Violeta O. Shvets
Odessa National Polytechnic University, Odessa, Ukraine
ORCID: 0000-0002-9288-5824
Email: Violettasvec234@gmail.com

Received 16.01.2021

*Добрянська Н.А., Дем'янюк А.А., Швець В.О. Аналіз
нелегальної міграції та державна політика щодо її усунення.
Оглядова стаття.*

В даній статті досліджено нелегальну міграцію та політику щодо її усунення. Описуються основні характеристики міграції. Визначаються позитивні та негативні сторони такого багатогранного сучасного явища, як міграція населення. Особлива увага звертається на проблему нелегальної міграції. Називаються загрози, які можуть виникати з її збільшенням. Виявляються методи усунення нелегальної міграції та проблеми державної політики щодо її усунення. Пропонуються засоби протидії нелегальної міграції. Охарактеризовуються інструменти, завдяки яким можна боротися з нелегальною міграцією. Проаналізовано світові тенденції нелегальної міграції. Проведено аналітична характеристика масштабів нелегальної міграції України. Запропоновано основні напрями протидії нелегальної міграції.

Ключові слова: міграція, держава, державна політика, мігранти, виїзд, грошовий переказ

*Dobrianska N.A., Demyanyuk A.A., Shvets V.O. Analysis of
illegal migration and government policy to eliminate it. Review
article.*

This article examines illegal migration and policies to eliminate it. The main characteristics of migration are described. The positive and negative sides of such a multifaceted modern phenomenon as population migration are determined. Particular attention is paid to the problem of illegal migration. The threats that may arise with its increase are called. Methods of elimination of illegal migration and problems of state policy on its elimination are revealed. Means of counteraction to illegal migration are offered. The tools that can be used to combat illegal migration are described. Global trends in illegal migration are analyzed. The analytical characteristic of scales of illegal migration of Ukraine is carried out. The main directions of combating illegal migration are proposed.

Keywords: migration, state, state policy, migrants, departure, money transfer

Rellevance of the topic is due, first of all, with the importance of defining scientific approaches on migration policy on macro level. Implementation of imperfect migration policy enhances its negative consequences to which can be attributed: an increase in illegal migration, the unconstructive economic activity of migrants, the growth of economic chaos, increased social tension, increasing the risks of interethnic, interethnic, interconfessional and other conflicts, deterioration of the criminogenic situation; Sailed part of cash income, etc. At present, in the world, because of the escalation of many conflicts, among the population, the opinions of the state should be introduced more rigorous measures to terminate the negative impact of migration processes on the situation in the state.

Analysis of recent research and publications

Over the past few decades, one of the manifestations of globalization was the strengthening of international labor migration. Which is due to the involvement of international migration streams of a number of independent countries, which for a long time due to historical circumstances did not participate in the process of international labor migration. For such countries, in particular for Ukraine, the entry into the global system of international labor flows is relatively new and insufficiently controlled by the state level.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

The article is devoted to the analysis of approaches to understanding illegal labor migration. It

is necessary to determine the features of this phenomenon, analyze the statistics of illegal migration in Ukraine. To find out nature, causes and factors those promote illegal labor migration in Ukraine.

The aim of the article is to study factors leading to the intensification of migration processes, analyzing illegal migration and consequences for the economic system of the country; study of mechanisms of state - legal regulation of the problem of illegal migration.

The main part

In 2018, in the annual Ukrainian citizenship index, Ukraine has made a serious breakthrough on 17 positions and showed one of the most impressive results of the growth of citizenship in the world.

The Index of Citizens of the World (The Henley & Partners – Kochenov Quality of Natery Index, Qni) provides an objective assessment of 209 world citizenship and ranks them according to various indicators.

The leader of the updated passport index, which determines how many countries can be visited with one or another passport, became Japan. Citizens of this country can visit without a visa of 190 countries. In the second place South Korea, which has added India in a list of visa-free countries and rose in an index to one position. Singapore also in second place with an indicator of 189 countries.

In 2017, Germany ranked first with the figure of 177 countries, but in 2018, Germany divided the third place with France (188 visa visiting countries).

Great Britain and the United States lost positions in the index, and in 2018 the 6th place (185 countries) took. Significant fall from the 1st place in 2015 Experts explain to the policies of "closed doors" of both countries [1].

Ukrainians thanks to a visa-free regime with the EU generally have visa-free access in 128 countries. Ukraine occupies the 41st place of 104. The same indicator in Nicaragua and Samoa.

Thus, at the end of 2018, citizens of Ukraine had the right to the visa-free procedure of entry to countries of the world:

- on the basis of a passport of a citizen of Ukraine for departure abroad;
- on the basis of a diplomatic passport;
- on the basis of a service passport.

Simplified procedure for entry into the territory of a foreign state on the basis of a passport of a citizen of Ukraine for traveling abroad (arrangement visa, e-visa) introduced 59 countries.

According to the analysis of trips abroad (Table 1), the largest citizens of Ukraine travel abroad with a private goal. The share of such trips in the total number of trips abroad is not less than 97% [2].

Table 1. Analysis of the number of visits of Ukrainian citizens abroad

Year	Indicators	the purpose of the trip					In total
		employment	organized	private	staff	military service	
2015 year	number	185 170	206 598	22 779 483	193 530	14	23 364 795
	share,%	0.79	0.88	97.49	0.83	-	100,00
2016 year	number	156 157	224 646	24 287 430	557 920	230	25 226 383
	share,%	0.62	0.89	96.28	2.21	-	100,00
2017 year	number	97 271	120 887	26 219 255	629 548	114	27 067 075
	share,%	0.36	0.45	96.87	2.33	-	100,00
2018 year	number	97 010	224 420	27 489 462	165 789	-	27 976 681
	share,%	0.35	0.80	98.26	0.59	-	100,00
In total		535 610	776 553	100 775 921	1 546 792	358	103 635 234

Source: compiled by authors on materials [3].

After analyzing the data in the table, we can conclude that for 2015, private travel abroad (22 779483, or 97.49%), and the least in military service (14), in just 2015, 23 364 795 trips were carried out. In 2016, private travel abroad (24 287 430, or 96.28%), and the least in the military service (230), in just 2016, 25 226 383 trips abroad were carried out. For 2017, private travel abroad (26 219 255, or 96.87%) was carried out, and the least in military service (114), in just 2017, 27 067 075 trips abroad were made.

In 2018, private travel abroad (27489462, or 98.26%) was most accomplished, and the smallest service trips (97 010, or 0.35%), in just 2018, 27 976 681 travel abroad were made. In total, for 2015-2018, 103 635 234 travel abroad was made, of them are 535 610, organized – 776553, private – 100 775 921, service staff – 1 546 792, on military service – 358.

The most visited countries of the world for Ukrainian citizens were Poland (40068412), Russia (16910441), Hungary (11677203), Moldova (6794490), Belarus (5257392), Turkey (3913047), Romania (3896704), Slovakia (3413805) and Egypt (3413805) and Egypt (3413805) 2641355).

During 2015-2018, the direction of trips of Ukrainian citizens finally moved to the EU. Total to EU member states Citizens of Ukraine went 65268928 times.

According to analytical data of the IMF, migration flows are characterized by a greater share of highly educated migrants that confirms an increase in the scale of the intelligence. If in the 2000s immigration flows to highly developed world economies were characterized by the interest rate "Full Higher Education" – "Secondary Education" – "Initial Education" 34% – 26% – 40%, then in 2018, these

figures indicated at 40% – 29% – 31% respectively. Ukraine now occupies the best places in international rankings of the most secure countries (Index The

Global Peace Index¹), Economic Freedom (Index of Economic Freedom), happiness (Index of Happiness), the lightness of doing business, global (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Ukraine in international indices in 2015-2019

Source: compiled by authors on materials [1].

After considering the drawing, we can conclude that in the global index of 2018 peacefulness, Ukraine has occupied 152th among other countries. In the 2019 economic freedom index, Ukraine occupied 150th place. In the index of happiness from 2015 to 2017, Ukraine has occupied 138th place. In the index of sustainable development in 2016, Ukraine has occupied 102 place. In the index of attracting countries in international trade in 2016, Ukraine took 95th place. In the index of sustainable development in 2016, Ukraine ranked 85th. In the Index of Human Development 2018, Ukraine ranked 81th. In the index of global competition, Ukraine ranks 81th. In the index of productive business in 2018, Ukraine took 71th place. In the 2018 logistics performance index,

Ukraine took 66th place. In the global index of innovations in 2018, Ukraine took 43th place. And according to the index of sustainable development, Ukraine ranks 36th.

Near the countries of Europe and Central Asia, Ukraine has been a largest recipient from their foreign migrants for several years and includes up to 10 countries with the highest proportion of transfers in the gross domestic product (Table 2). It is worth paying attention to the fact that the amount of revenues to Ukraine reached a new historical maximum, and the significance of these funds for the welfare of households who receive them is difficult to overestimate [4].

Table 2. Transfers of external migrants by the countries of their greatest income

Country to which Transfers from migrants come	Transfers volume, billion dollars. USA	Number permanent population, thousands of people	The sum of the transfers of calculation person, dollars.	Share of transfers in gross domestic product, %
Indonesia	11237	273524	41.1	1.1
Belgium	11450	11482	997.2	2.1
Spain	12301	46693	263.4	0.9
Ukraine	14378	44246	325.0	11.4
Bangladesh	15496	161377	96.0	5.4
Vietnam	15934	95546	166.8	6.6
Germany	17364	83124	208.9	0.4
Pakistan	21014	212228	99.0	6.8
Nigeria	24311	195875	124.1	6.1
France	26428	64991	406.6	0.9
Egypt	28918	98424	293.8	11.6
Philippines	33827	106651	317.2	10.2
Mexico	35659	126191	282.6	3.0
PRC	67414	1427648	47.2	0.5
India	78609	1352642	58.1	2.9

Source: compiled by authors on materials [1].

After analyzing the table, we can conclude that the largest transfers from migrants comes to India (78609 billion dollars), and least to Indonesia (11237 billion dollars). The number of permanent population is the largest in the PRC (1427648 thousand people), and the smallest in Belgium (11482 thousand people). The amount of transfers per person is largest in Belgium (997.2 dollars), and the smallest amount of transfers per person in Indonesia (41.1 dollars). The share of transfers in the gross domestic product is largest in Egypt (11.6%), and the smallest in Germany (0.4%).

In general, macroeconomic consequences of large-scale money transfers are rather complicated and contradictory and directly influence the safety of the socio-economic sector.

Of course, positive are: the growth of national income (in the event that money transfers are transmitted through official channels); acquisition by the recipient of the reputation of creditworthiness on international credit markets; acquisition by the recipient country of the possibility of stabilizing the balance of accounts of the national balance of

payments; Increasing consumption and associated with this creation of new jobs.

However, in the absence of effective state policy, in particular, with regard to stimulating and directing from migrants received, there are also negative consequences associated, first of all, with increased risks: rising prices of national currency and corresponding negative impact on exports; an increase in inflation; Reducing the aggregate supply of labor and slowing the employment of the unemployed.

Today, strengthening the impact of demographic factors on the scale of labor migration is manifested in Western Europe, the United States and Russia, where the low growth of the population and the aging of the nation are largely offset by immigrants. Thus, net immigration provides 56% demographic growth in developed regions, in particular in Western European countries – 89%. Today in countries – the main recipients of the foreign labor force the share of foreigners is 5-20% of the total population, or 10-25% of the economically active part. Consider immigration compensators for 2000-2050 (Table 3).

Table 3. Immigration Compensators for 2000-2050, thousands of perpetrators per 1 million inhabitants every year

Country	Immigration needed to maintain the number of able-bodied population (15-64 years old)	Immigration required to preserve the ratio of the number of older persons over 65 and individuals / ages 15-64
Germany	6.0	44.8
Italy	6.5	39.8
France	1.8	30.4
USA	1.3	43.2
Japan	5.1	85.6
Russia	2.1	20.3

Source: composed by authors on materials [4].

By considering the table, we can conclude that the greatest emigration needed to maintain the number of able-bodied population in Italy (6.5 thousand people), and the smallest emigration, which is necessary to maintain the number of able-bodied population in the United States (1.3 thousand people). The greatest immigration required to preserve the co-opinion of the number of older persons over 65 years and persons aged 15-64 in Japan (85.6 thousand people), and the smallest in Russia (20.3 thousand people).

It should be noted that for the period up to 2050 will most require compensatory net immigration by countries such as Germany (almost 45 thousand people per 1 million inhabitants each year), Italy (39.8 thousand), France (30.4), USA (43.2 thousand), Japan (82.6 thousand). Even Russia will require about 20.3 thousand foreigners per 1 million inhabitants (Table 3).

We emphasize that significant changes in innovation and technological development of countries were related to the migration of high qualification specialists. As a result of the formation of global scientific and educational space, international mobility of intellectual personnel in the conditions of rapid development of international information and communication networks was

particularly intensified [3; 8].

According to the International Labor Organization, the world's number of employed labor, for example, in 1980 amounted to about 1 billion people, and in 2018 this figure reached 2.9 billion people. We will present the dynamics of regional unemployment, as one of the significant factors influencing migration processes during 2010-2019 (Table 4).

After analyzing the table, we can conclude that the greatest unemployment rate in the world as a whole for the period 2010-2019 in 2019 – 6.1%, and the smallest level in 2010 – 5.5%. The largest unemployment rate in developed countries and EU member states was in 2017-2019 – 8.6%, and the smallest in 2010 – 5.8%. The largest unemployment rate in Central and South-Eastern Europe (not members of the EU) and CIS member states in 2019 – 8.3%, and the smallest in 2017 – 8.0%. The greatest unemployment rate in the Middle East countries was in 2019 – 11%, and the smallest in 2010 – 10.2%. The largest level of unemployment in North Africa was in 2018-2019 – 12.2%, and the smallest in 2010 – 11.1%. The greatest unemployment rate in the Africa in the south of Sahara was in 2017-2019 – 7.6%, and the smallest in 2010 – 7.5%. The largest

unemployment rate in Latin America and the Caribbean was in 2010 – 6.9%, and the smallest in 2018-2019 – 6.5%. The greatest level of unemployment in East Asia was in 2019 – 4.7%, and the smallest in 2010 – 3.8%. The greatest level of

unemployment in the countries of Southeast Asia and the Pacific Basin was in 2010 – 5.5%, and the smallest in 2017 – 4.1%. The greatest unemployment rate in South Asia was in 2010 and 2019 – 4.1%, and the smallest in 2017 – 3.9%.

Table 4. Dynamics of level of regional unemployment during 2010-2019,%

Group of countries	2010 y.	2017 y.	2018 y.	2019 y.
The world in general	5.5	6.0	6.0	6.1
Developed countries and EU member states	5.8	8.6	8.6	8.6
Countries of Central and Southeastern Europe (non-EU members) and CIS member countries	8.2	8.0	8.2	8.3
Middle East countries	10.2	10.9	10.9	11.0
North Africa countries	11.1	12.1	12.2	12.2
Africa countries south of Sahara	7.5	7.6	7.6	7.6
Latin America and Caribbean	6.9	6.6	6.5	6.5
East Asian countries	3.8	4.4	4.5	4.7
Countries of Southeast Asia and Pacific Basin	5.5	4.1	4.2	4.3
South Asian countries	4.1	3.9	4.0	4.1

Source: compiled by authors on materials [2].

According to the statistical data of the International Labor Organization in 2018, the number of unemployed in the world has reached 202 million people, which is 5 million more than in 2017. According to the forecasts of the International Labor Organization, the unemployment rate will reach 215 million people for 2020. In 2015, the highest unemployment was celebrated by North Africa (12.1%) and middle-eastern countries (10.9%), high-developed EU economies and EU member states (8.4%) [5].

In Ukraine, migrants live in the following countries: Russia (about 3.4 million); Kazakhstan, Belarus and Uzbekistan (about 250 thousand), as well as Moldova (about 200 thousand). Recall Ukraine ranked 78th in the annual rating index of democracy-

2019, published by the Economist magazine, improving its indicators for six points compared to 2018.

The duration of work abroad of the vast majority of Ukrainian workers, which returned to Ukraine, does not exceed one year (29% – worked more than a year, 14% – several years). The number of internally displaced persons, as a result of the conflict in the Donbass, is 1.6 million people. The structure of employment of internally displaced persons in Ukraine: – 9% of the economically active population (growth forecast for the nearest period – 50%); 20% are officially employed, others work under oral deals or consider themselves self-employed. Countries of the appointment of Ukrainian labor migrants are presented in Fig. 2-4.

Figure 2. The main countries of the appointment of Ukrainian labor migrants in 2018-2019

Source: compiled by authors on materials [5].

By considering the drawing, we can conclude that in 2018-2019, the main countries of the appointment of Ukrainian labor migrants were Russia (30%), Poland (21%), Italy (11%), Czech Republic (15%), Belarus (3%), other countries (20%). The largest

percentage falls on Russia (30%), and the smallest in Belarus (3%).

After analyzing the diagram, we can conclude that the main countries of the appointment of Ukrainian labor migrants in 2018-2019 were Russia – 26.3%,

Poland – 38.9%, Italy – 11.3%, Czech Republic – 9.4%, USA – 1.8%, Belarus – 1.7%, Portugal – 1.6%, Hungary – 1.3%, Israel – 1.1%, Finland – 1%,

Germany – 0.8%, Other countries – 4.8%. The largest percentage falls into Poland – 38.9%, and the smallest Germany – 0.8%.

Figure 3. The main countries of the appointment of Ukrainian labor migrants in 2018-2019

Source: compiled by authors on materials [5].

The volume of international labor migration in Ukraine in 2019 amounted to 688000 people, including 423800 long-term (migration is at least 1 year) and 264400 short-term migrant labor (Fig. 4). In addition, about 3100000 people expressed their intention to migrate in the next 12 months, which is about 45% of the current volume. In Ukraine, the internal mobility of the population is twice as large as the number of external labor migrants (1643000

people). The total domestic migration in 2019 was 9% of the economically active population in Ukraine. It is expected that the annual pace of internal mobility in 2019-2020 will increase by about 50%. The volumes of migrations according to this survey are smaller than the data survey of the State Statistics Committee and IDSD. M. V. Ptukha NASO, obviously, is due to a decrease in the level of frankness of respondents in crisis conditions [6].

Figure 4. Assessment of the number of different categories of migrants in Ukraine for 2019-2020.

Source: compiled by authors on materials [6].

By considering the drawing, we can conclude that in 2019-2020, the number of different categories of migrants in Ukraine has suffered: potential internal labor migrants – 828700, potential short-term migrants – 192600, potential long-term migrants – 117300, labor migrants, which Returned – 144400, internal labor migrants – 1 643 000, short-term labor migrants – 264400, long-term labor migrants – 423 800. The largest number in the category of internal labor migrants, and the smallest in the category 117 300.

If you analyze the purpose of staying abroad from migrants from Ukraine in 2018-2019, then the work determines the trips of 87.9% of migrants, training 5.3%, reunification of the family (3.8%).

The smallest percentage falls on forced migration (0.5%), etc.

Conclusions

Consequently, the intensity of migration processes in the modern world is steadily increasing. At the present stage there is an increase in intellectual migration, in addition, in the era of the information economy, within which the virtualization of production processes is increasingly acquiring, the workforce is involved through the online outsourcing tools (quasimigration processes). Online outsourcing today is a promising alternative to traditional forms of employment, representing a more flexible and ambulance system of hiring through online platforms.

On the decision to implement emigration affects the following factors: a high level of qualification (in the development of a modern knowledge economy, the educational level of the migrant provides its successful competitiveness in the labor market); the possibility of successful integration in the destination country (network support, including interpersonal connections of migrants, the presence of community organizations compatriots in recipient countries); minimum cultural distance, etc.). Ability to diversify sources of income due to emigration; intensive development of transnational companies that are powerful cultural, innovation and technological centers of the world economy (they contribute to the dissemination of links between countries, etc. stimulate the development of migration processes); Development of the transport system (facilitates migration), etc.

In the modern world, six main centers of labor force were formed: North America, Western and Central Europe, oil-building countries of the Middle East, the countries of the Asia-Pacific region, Latin

America, a group of separate countries of Central and South Africa. Significant socio-economic and cultural potential of the countries of Eastern Europe allows you to hope that in the conditions of successful adaptation and implementation of the experience of forming and implementing mechanisms of migration policy of developed countries, they have the opportunity to become a new large-scale center of gravity of labor [7; 9].

The probable preservation of positive migration growth in Eastern Europe will not only provide sustainable population growth in the coming decades, but also contributes to the gain of the aging of the population and smooth the age structure of the population.

However, immigration becomes a challenge for individual countries. Thus, the arrival of illegal migrants (in particular to Poland, Romania and Slovakia) can cause transformations of the mental characteristics of the population of the relevant countries, which is a significant socio-demographic problem and even a threat to national security.

Abstract

This article examines illegal migration and policies to eliminate it. The main characteristics of migration are described. The positive and negative sides of such a multifaceted modern phenomenon as population migration are determined. Particular attention is paid to the problem of illegal migration. The threats that may arise with its increase are called. Methods of elimination of illegal migration and problems of state policy on its elimination are revealed. Means of counteraction to illegal migration are offered. The tools that can be used to combat illegal migration are described. Global trends in illegal migration are analyzed. The analytical characteristic of scales of illegal migration of Ukraine is carried out. The main directions of combating illegal migration are proposed. The urgency of the topic is primarily related to the importance of defining scientific approaches to migration policy at the macro level. The introduction of imperfect migration policy exacerbates its negative consequences, which include: increased illegal migration, unconstructive economic activity of migrants, growing economic chaos, increasing social tensions, increasing risks of interethnic, interethnic, interfaith and other conflicts, worsening crime; outflow of cash income, etc. Now, in the world, due to the escalation of many conflicts, the population is of the opinion that the state should take tougher measures to stop the negative impact of migration on the situation in the country. The article is devoted to the analysis of approaches to understanding illegal labor migration. The peculiarities of this phenomenon are determined, the statistics of illegal migration in Ukraine are analyzed. The nature, causes and factors that contribute to illegal labor migration in Ukraine have been clarified. The definitions of "illegal labor migration" and "combating illegal labor migration" are proposed. The purpose of the article is to study the factors that lead to the intensification of migration processes, analysis of illegal migration and the consequences for the economic system of the country; study of mechanisms of state - legal regulation of the problem of illegal migration.

Список літератури:

1. Мойсей В.І. Зовнішні економічні ефекти міжнародної міграції робочої сили: автореф. дис. на здобуття наук. ступ. к.е.н., спеціальність 08.00.02 — світове господарство і міжнародні економічні відносини Львів. – 2015.
2. Конвенція Міжнародної організації праці «Про трудящих мігрантів» (переглянута 1949 року) від 1 липня 1949 року № 97.
3. Дахно І. Міжнародна економіка: навч. посіб. / Іван Дахно, Юлія Бовтрук; Міжнар. акад. управл. персонал. – К.: МАУП. – 2002. – 120 с.
4. Трубич С. Міграційні процеси і зайнятість населення // Вісник Львівського університету. – Сер. Міжнародні відносини. – 1999. – Вип. 1. – С. 398-403.
5. Липов В. Міжнародна економіка: навчальний посібник/ Володимир Липов; Міністерство освіти і науки України, ХНЕУ. – Харків: ВД «ІНЖЕК». – 2005. – 30 с.
6. Володько В. Ціннісні орієнтації сучасних українських трудових мігрантів (соціокультурний підхід): Магістерська робота. – Львів: ЛНУ ім. І. Франка (Центр магістерських програм). – 2006. – 100 с.
7. Чехович С.Б. Елементарний курс міграційного права України: конспект лекцій: навчальний посібник для студентів вищих навчальних закладів. – К.: МАУП. – 2004. – 216 с.

8. Данюк М., Леоненко О. Удосконалення державної міграційної політики України // Україна: аспекти праці. – 2007. – №6. – С.47-51.
9. Добрянська Н.А., Буковський Д.А. Реформа децентралізації як засіб формування ефективного самоврядування в Україні // Економіка: реалії часу. Науковий журнал. – 2020. – № 1 (47). – с. 57-67. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://economics.opu.ua/ejopu/2020/No1/57.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/ETR.01.2020.3. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3967330.
10. Dobrianska N.A. The current state of investments attraction into the regional economy / N. A. Dobrianska, L. A. Torishnya // Економічний журнал Одеського політехнічного університету. – 2019. – № 1 (7). – С. 5-12. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://economics.opu.ua/ejopu/2019/No1/5.pdf>. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3405936.

References:

1. Moisei V.I. (2015). External economic effects of international labor migration. Extended abstract of candidate's thesis. Lviv.
2. Convention of the International Labor Organization "On Migrant Workers" (revised in 1949) of July 1, 1949 № 97.
3. Dakhno I., Bovtruk J. (2002). International Economics. International. acad. management personnel. – K.: MAUP.
4. Trubych S. (1999). Migration processes and employment. Visnyk of Lviv National University. Series: International relations, 1, 398-403.
5. Lipov V. (2005). International economics. Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, KhNEU. Kharkiv: VD "INZHEK".
6. Volodko V. (2006). Value orientations of modern Ukrainian labor migrants (socio-cultural approach): Master's thesis. Lviv: LNU named after I. Franko (Center for Master's Programs).
7. Chekhovich S.B. (2004). Elementary course of migration law of Ukraine: lecture notes: a textbook for students of higher educational institutions. K.: MAUP.
8. Danyuk M., Leontenko O. (2007). Improving the state migration policy of Ukraine. Ukraine: aspects of labor, 6, 47-51.
9. Dobrianska N.A., Bukovsky D.A. (2020). Decentralization reform as a means of forming effective local self-government in Ukraine. Economics: time realities. Scientific journal, 1 (47), 20-26. Retrieved from <https://economics.opu.ua/files/archive/2020/No1/20.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/ETR.01.2020.3. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3967330.
10. Dobrianska N.A., Torishnya L.A. (2019). The current state of investments attraction into the regional economy. Economic journal Odessa polytechnic university, 1 (7), 5-12. Retrieved from <https://economics.opu.ua/ejopu/2019/No1/5.pdf>. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3405936.

Посилання на статтю:

Dobrianska N.A. Analysis of illegal migration and government policy to eliminate it / N. A. Dobrianska, A. A. Demyanyuk, V. O. Shvets // Економіка: реалії часу. Науковий журнал. – 2021. – № 2 (54). – С. 24-31. – Режим доступу до журн.: <https://economics.net.ua/files/archive/2021/No2/24.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/ETR.02.2021.3. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5115796.

Reference a Journal Article:

Dobrianska N.A. Analysis of illegal migration and government policy to eliminate it / N. A. Dobrianska, A. A. Demyanyuk, V. O. Shvets // Economics: time realities. Scientific journal. – 2021. – № 2 (54). – P. 24-31. – Retrieved from <https://economics.net.ua/files/archive/2021/No2/24.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/ETR.02.2021.3. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5115796.

